

Original Article

Elevated TSH Levels: A Database Study of General Practitioners' Course of Action

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To investigate general practitioners' course of action after detection of elevated thyroid stimulating hormone (TSH) levels regarding repeat testing, direct levothyroxine replacement, or neither.

Methods: We conducted a retrospective study of adults without prior evidence of thyroid disease and with a first detection of elevated TSH levels from January 1, 2015, to December 31, 2020, using data from electronic medical records of a Swiss primary care database. We determined the occurrence of either repeat TSH testing or direct levothyroxine initiation in primary care during 12-month follow-up and determined associations with demographic and clinical factors.

Results: Of the 1 591 patients included (median age 65 years, 64.4% female, median TSH 5.7 mIU/L), 34.3% received repeat TSH testing and 12.4% received direct levothyroxine replacement in primary care during follow-up. Repeat TSH testing showed the strongest association with overt hypothyroidism and was more common among patients with high primary care utilization and among patients aged 40–64 years compared to patients aged <40 years. Direct levothyroxine initiation was more likely for TSH levels >7 mIU/L, overt hypothyroidism, female patients, and nonurban practices. **Conclusions:** While the degree of thyroid dysfunction was the main driver of follow-up, we identified important gaps in the primary care-based monitoring of elevated TSH levels in young patients and in patients with infrequent consultations. We also observed potential overtreatment of women and patients in nonurban areas. Our findings highlight the need for standardization and dissemination of guidelines for the management of elevated TSH levels among general practitioners.

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Introduction

Primary hypothyroidism is a common endocrine disorder characterized by elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels affecting up to 8% of the European population.¹ On one hand, its early detection by means of TSH level measurements is essential to prevent morbidity. On the other hand, recent data suggest that many thyroid function tests, as well as subsequent replacement with levothyroxine (LT4), may be inappropriate.^{2–4} Overuse of thyroid testing may lead to overtreatment with LT4, which is potentially associated with cost and harms primarily from cardiac

and skeletal side effects,^{5,6} and is therefore considered low-value care.⁷

Recommendations for TSH screening in asymptomatic, nonpregnant individuals are conflicting. While some guidelines advise for regular assessment of thyroid function in the general population,⁸ others argue that current evidence is insufficient to recommend for or against routine screening.^{9,10} Similarly, guidelines are divided on recommendations for LT4 replacement in subclinical hypothyroidism, with some generally discouraging it¹¹ and some advocating replacement in specific cases.¹² At the same time, many of the typical symptoms of hypothyroidism can also be caused by a variety of similarly common conditions, making them poorly specific.¹³ Combined with inconsistent guideline recommendations, this may contribute to the high variation in thyroid care among clinicians that has been noted previously.^{14–16} In addition, concerns have been raised that LT4 replacement may

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occur in the presence of borderline elevated TSH levels or in the absence of confirmed TSH elevation,^{3,4} contradicting explicit recommendations to use repeat TSH testing to confirm a diagnosis of hypothyroidism.¹²

While previous analyses have focused on the appropriateness of TSH screening or of LT4 replacement, there are little data on the response of general practitioners (GPs) to the detection of elevated TSH levels. The aim of this study was therefore to investigate the course of action following an initial finding of elevated TSH levels in Swiss primary care, focusing on repeat TSH testing and on direct LT4 replacement.

Materials and Methods

Setting and Data Source

We conducted a retrospective study based on data from the Family medicine Research using Electronic medical records (FIRE) project hosted by the Institute of Primary Care of the University of Zurich.¹⁷ The FIRE database has been collecting structured routine data from electronic medical records of over 700 general practitioners from German-speaking Switzerland since 2009. It contains laboratory test results, medication prescriptions coded according to the Anatomic Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) Classification System,¹⁸ reasons for encounters coded according to the International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC-2) system,¹⁹ blood pressure measurements, biometric data (body height and weight), and demographic data (gender and year of birth). Individual patients are anonymized, but their consultations can be followed over time within individual practices.

Since they fall outside the scope of the Federal Act on Research involving Human Beings (BASEC-Nr. Req-2017-00797), the local Ethics Committee of the Canton of Zurich waived ethical approval for studies based on data from the FIRE project (in particular, no patient consent was required due to anonymization).²⁰ We report the results of our analyses following the *REporting of studies Conducted using Observational Routinely-collected health Data* (RECORD) guidelines.²¹

Study Cohorts and Outcomes

We defined an inclusion period ranging from January 1, 2015, to December 31, 2020, and included all patients with at least 1 elevated TSH level recorded during this inclusion period as eligible cases. The date of the respective first TSH measurement indicating an elevated TSH level during the inclusion period defined a patient's time of inclusion. We identified elevated TSH levels according to the upper reference limit provided along with the recorded test result. If no upper reference limit was available, we used the most common among the reported upper reference limits. We categorized TSH levels at inclusion into <7 mIU/L (mild elevation), 7–10 mIU/L (moderate elevation), and >10 mIU/L (severe elevation) according to differing recommendations for these ranges.^{8,10,12,22} To ensure a first detection of elevated TSH, we excluded all patients without a consultation at least 2 years prior to inclusion and all patients with a history of elevated TSH levels prior to inclusion. For each patient, we defined an individual follow-up period of 12 months starting from inclusion. We then excluded all patients aged <18 years at inclusion, all patients with a history of LT4 replacement before inclusion, all patients with any evidence of overt hypothyroidism before inclusion, and all patients with evidence of hyperthyroidism, iodine deficiency, pregnancy, or prescription of medications with antithyroid effects at any time before end of follow-up (see [Supplementary Table 1](#) for the operationalized criteria). We analyzed the course of action of the GPs by

Highlights

- Elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) levels are often found in primary care.
- Only 35% of patients receive repeat testing after detection of TSH elevation.
- Repeat testing is rarer in younger patients with few primary care visits.
- Levothyroxine initiation is more common in women and patients in non-urban areas.

Clinical Relevance

Thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) elevation is often found in primary care, and the subsequent course of action is critical to patients with potential hypothyroidism. In this study, we examined the frequency and factors associated with repeat TSH testing and direct levothyroxine replacement after detection of TSH elevation in primary care.

considering the following complementary outcomes during follow-up.

- repeat TSH testing, defined as the occurrence of a TSH testing request prior to any potential LT4 replacement,
- direct LT4 replacement, defined as the occurrence of an LT4 prescription prior to any confirmation of a TSH elevation,
- the occurrence of neither repeat TSH testing nor direct LT4 replacement.

For both the exclusion criteria and the outcome definition, we identified LT4 replacement as the prescription of ATC codes H03AA01 (levothyroxine sodium) or H03AA03 (combinations of levothyroxine and liothyronine). The FIRE database contains no prescriptions of any other ATC codes in the group H03AA (thyroid hormones), meaning that LT4 prescription can be understood as the most general form of thyroid hormone replacement in this study.

Explanatory Variables

For each patient, we considered the following explanatory variables: gender, age at inclusion, TSH levels at inclusion, and overt hypothyroidism at inclusion defined as presence of free thyroxine (fT4) levels below the lower reference limit within 4 weeks from inclusion. In addition, we determined the number of consultations recorded during 1 year preceding inclusion as a proxy for primary care utilization. We also considered presence of cardiovascular disease, diabetes, and dyslipidemia at any time during or before follow-up as relevant comorbidities that may further influence decisions on thyroid care (see [Supplementary Table 1](#) for the operationalized identification criteria). To explore the factors associated with variation between GPs, we considered their gender, age, workload (defined as the number of consultations per 5-day working week during the previous year), and urbanity of their practice location (according to the Swiss Federal Statistical Office²³).

Statistical Analyses

We summarize variables as counts and percentages or medians with interquartile ranges (IQRs) as appropriate. Crude comparisons of characteristics of cohort patients of different TSH level categories

at inclusion are provided in terms of chi-squared tests for categorical and Kruskal–Wallis tests for continuous variables, using *P*-values to assess statistical significance at a 0.05 level.

To analyze the choice of the course of action among the 3 possible outcomes of direct LT4 replacement, repeat TSH testing, and neither we fitted a multinomial logistic regression model among the study cohort. Multinomial logistic regression provides a generalization of binary logistic regression for categorical outcome variables that can assume more than 2 values.²⁴ As with binary logistic regression, one of the possible values of the outcome variable is declared as a reference, and the associations of various covariates are expressed in terms of effects for all remaining values of the outcome variable versus this reference. In our case, we chose the occurrence of neither TSH testing or LT4 replacement as the reference outcome. For adjustment, we used patient gender, age (categorized into <40, 40–64, 65–79, and ≥80 years), presence of comorbidities (each binary), number of consultations during the year preceding inclusion (in tertiles) as patient-level covariates. GP gender, age (in tertiles), workload (in tertiles), and urbanity of practice location were used as GP-level adjustment covariates. To account for clustering of patients within the respective treating GPs, we fitted a mixed-effects model using normally distributed GP-level random effects. We report coefficient estimates in terms of adjusted odds ratios (AORs) for each of repeat TSH testing and direct LT4 replacement versus neither action with corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CIs). To quantify variation across GPs, we report estimates of the median odds ratios (MORs) from a null model that did not contain any GP-level covariates. The MOR can be interpreted as the median relative odds of the respective outcome for a given patient when switching randomly between GPs.²⁵ We estimated each one MOR for direct LT4 replacement and one for repeat TSH testing with respect to neither action during follow-up.

To assess the effect of imputing upper reference limits for TSH where missing, we conducted a sensitivity analysis using the lowest of the upper reference limits most frequently reported in the database (affecting at least 1% of all TSH tests), repeating both the descriptive analyses and the regression modelling.

We conducted all statistical analyses with the statistical software R version 4.1.0 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria).²⁶ We used the package *mclogit* for mixed-effects multinomial regression.²⁷ Missing demographic data were handled by case-wise deletion for descriptive analyses and by list-wise deletion for regression modelling.

Results

Cohort Characteristics

Among the 800 768 patients approached during the inclusion period, 148 738 received at least 1 TSH measurement, and 10 332 were eligible cases with at least 1 elevated TSH. After applying the exclusion criteria, the final study cohort consisted of 1 591 patients (median age 65 years, IQR 50–77, 64.4% female). The median TSH at inclusion was 5.7 mIU/L (IQR 5.1–6.9), and 9.4% of patients had overt hypothyroidism at inclusion. We observed no significant difference in age ($P = .10$) or gender structure ($P = .72$) between different TSH categories at inclusion. Patients with lower TSH levels at inclusion were more likely to have diabetes ($P = .006$). The cohort patients were treated by 328 GPs (median age at earliest inclusion 50 years, IQR 44–57, 39.0% female, 73.2% in urban practices, median workload 72.0 consultations per working week, IQR 50.7–103.1). [Table](#) summarizes the cohort characteristics stratified by TSH levels at inclusion, and [Fig 1](#) illustrates the selection process. The most commonly reported upper reference limit for TSH was 4.78 mIU/L

(see [Supplementary Table 2](#)) and was required for imputation due to missingness in 49.5% of all cohort patients.

Course of Action

Overall, 34.3% ($n = 546$) of the cohort patients received repeat TSH testing and 12.4% ($n = 197$) received direct LT4 replacement during the 12-month follow-up. Neither repeat TSH testing nor direct LT4 replacement occurred in 53.3% ($n = 848$) of patients. On multivariable adjustment, we found the strongest associations of repeat TSH testing with overt hypothyroidism at inclusion (AOR 2.74, 95% CI 1.70–4.42), a consultation count during the year preceding inclusion in the upper 2 tertiles (AOR versus first tertile 1.72, 95% CI 1.30–2.28 for the second and AOR 1.95, 95% CI 1.44–2.65 for the third tertile), and age 40–64 years (AOR versus <40 years 1.60, 95% CI 1.08–2.37). The MOR for repeat TSH testing was 1.51. Associations with direct LT4 replacement were strongest for TSH at inclusion over 10 mIU/L (AOR versus <7 mIU/L 9.02, 95% CI 5.38–15.11) and overt hypothyroidism at inclusion (AOR 6.60, 95% CI 3.86–11.28); the MOR was 1.53. The forest plot of [Fig 2](#) summarizes the estimated AORs. [Supplementary Table 3](#) provides detailed numerical results of the regression models.

The lowest of the most frequently reported upper reference limits for TSH was 4.0 mIU/L. The sensitivity analysis using this cutoff led to a cohort of 2106 patients, of whom 31.4% received repeat TSH testing, 10.0% received direct LT4 replacement, and 58.6% received neither action. The corresponding results are reported in the [Supplementary Tables 4](#) and [5](#)

Discussion

In this large database study, we examined GPs' course of action after detection of elevated TSH levels and found remarkably low rates of repeat TSH testing during 12-month follow-up. Younger patients and those with low primary care utilization were at increased risk of not receiving repeat TSH testing. Conversely, we found a modest incidence of unwarranted LT4 replacement without confirmed TSH elevation, which was associated with female gender and non-urban settings. By far, the strongest driver for both repeat TSH testing and direct LT4 replacement was strong laboratory evidence of reduced thyroid activity.

Patients in our study cohort were mainly aged 40–64 years and female. These demographics are similar to those of previous studies on the management of hypothyroidism in primary care.²⁸ We observed that patients aged 65 years or older were less likely to obtain direct LT4 replacement and that patients aged 40–64 years were more likely to obtain TSH monitoring than patients aged 40 years or younger, even after adjustment for baseline TSH and frequency of previous GP encounters. While the lower LT4 replacement rates may reflect a general awareness of recommendations based on diminishing benefits with advancing age,²⁹ these results also indicate that repeat TSH testing to confirm elevated levels tends to be missed in younger patients.

The strong associations of repeat TSH testing and direct LT4 replacement with overt hypothyroidism and with markedly elevated baseline TSH levels suggest that GPs base their decisions on laboratory parameters that are highly suggestive of impaired thyroid function. However, the low rates of repeat TSH testing are a cause for concern, as approximately half of patients with initially elevated TSH levels are not expected to have normalized TSH levels during follow-up.³⁰ While it is conceivable that GPs are aware of the debates surrounding the upper reference limit for TSH,³¹ the proportion of patients with no follow-up remains substantial, as it contradicts several recommendations to confirm TSH elevations within a few months.^{12,22} We also observed an association of

Table
Study cohort characteristics

Variable	TSH at inclusion			P-value
	Mild elevation <7 mIU/L n = 1 188	Moderate elevation 7-10 mIU/L n = 257	Severe elevation >10 mIU/L n = 146	
Patient age in years, n (%)				.10
<40	155 (13.0)	35 (13.6)	25 (17.1)	
40-64	399 (33.6)	105 (40.9)	57 (39.0)	
65-79	416 (35.0)	71 (27.6)	40 (27.4)	
≥80	218 (18.4)	46 (17.9)	24 (16.4)	
Female patients, n (%)	758 (63.8)	169 (65.8)	97 (66.4)	.72
Cardiovascular disease, n (%)	230 (19.4)	47 (18.3)	21 (14.4)	.34
Diabetes, n (%)	227 (19.1)	35 (13.6)	15 (10.3)	.006
Dyslipidemia, n (%)	375 (31.6)	78 (30.4)	36 (24.7)	.23
Body mass index in kg/m ² (most recent at inclusion), median (IQR)*	27.1 (23.5-31.4)	27.9 (24.2-31.8)	27.8 (24.1-33.5)	.38
Free thyroxine measurement at inclusion, n (%)	706 (59.4)	180 (70.0)	110 (75.3)	<.001
Overt hypothyroidism at inclusion, n (%)	66 (5.6)	21 (8.2)	62 (42.5)	<.001
Number of consultations during 1 year preceding inclusion, median (IQR)	6.0 (3.0-12.0)	5.0 (2.0-11.0)	5.0 (2.0-11.8)	.01
Urban location of practice, n (%)	820 (69.0)	178 (69.3)	91 (62.3)	.25
Course of action during 12-mo follow-up, n (%)				<.001
Repeat TSH testing	422 (35.5)	86 (33.5)	38 (26.0)	
Direct levothyroxine replacement	82 (6.9)	46 (17.9)	69 (47.3)	
Neither	684 (57.6)	125 (48.6)	39 (26.7)	

Stratification occurs by TSH level at inclusion. Abbreviations: IQR, interquartile range; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

* Body mass index was not documented for 54.3% of all cohort patients.

Figure 1. Study flowchart. Abbreviations: GPs, general practitioners; LT4, levothyroxine; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

monitoring with increasing primary care utilization before detection of elevated TSH, which may explain why these patients receive more laboratory tests, but does not justify that pathological test results would remain without consequences. It is possible that in these cases, GPs were aware of testing in a low pretest probability situation, or perhaps other factors were identified that better explained a particular reason for the encounter. Strictly speaking, however, repeat testing would still be indicated in these situations to rule out hypothyroidism as a comorbidity. On the other hand,

patients who do not visit their primary care physician frequently may require particularly rigorous repeat testing.

A considerable proportion of patients with mild to moderate TSH elevation at inclusion received direct LT4 replacement, suggesting potential overtreatment. According to guidelines, repeat testing for confirmation should precede LT4 prescription (with the possible exception of strongly elevated TSH levels).¹² A certain proportion of direct LT4 prescriptions may have been justified by severe clinical manifestations of new-onset hypothyroidism

Figure 2. Factors associated with the course of action during 12-month follow-up after detection of elevated TSH levels. As possible outcomes, we considered repeat TSH testing, direct LT4 replacement, and neither action. The forest plot shows adjusted odds ratios and corresponding 95% confidence intervals for repeat TSH testing and for direct LT4 replacement with respect to neither action derived from a multinomial logistic regression model. Abbreviations: GP, general practitioner; LT4, levothyroxine; TSH, thyroid-stimulating hormone.

requiring urgent hormone replacement, such as myxedema. However, their occurrence in primary care is very rare.^{28,32}

Our data do not reveal an excessive use of LT4 replacement in patients with borderline and unconfirmed TSH elevation suggested in older studies.⁴ In addition, we were unable to reproduce the previously observed higher rates of LT4 replacement in older patients.³³ This result may be the effect of updated hypothyroidism guidelines and more recent studies that do not support a benefit of LT4 replacement in subclinical hypothyroidism.^{29,34,35} Interestingly, we found no associations of direct LT4 replacement with

dyslipidemia, diabetes, or cardiovascular disease, despite their explicit mention in guidelines as situations that may require specific considerations.^{8,12} On the other hand, we observed an association between diabetes and lower TSH levels at inclusion. This may be explained by a higher propensity of patients with diabetes to receive excessive thyroid testing,³⁶ resulting in more near-normal test results.

The association between LT4 replacement and female gender, independently of baseline TSH and ft4 levels, is noteworthy. This finding contradicts self-reported decision making in an earlier

survey of Swiss GPs³⁷ but aligns with a more recent study on patients with subclinical hypothyroidism also based on electronic medical records.³² A small proportion of prescriptions may have occurred among women trying to become pregnant, who are occasionally mentioned as a group of patients with subclinical hypothyroidism for whom special considerations may apply.¹¹ However, the evidence for this indication has recently been considered insufficient.³⁸ Another explanation may be the fact that common symptoms of hypothyroidism are also more common presenting complaints of female patients in primary care, especially fatigue and gastrointestinal symptoms.^{28,39,40} However, the weak evidence for the efficacy of hormone replacement in subclinical hypothyroidism calls into question the role of such symptoms in the decision to initiate LT4 treatment.

Associations of demographic GP characteristics with either repeat TSH testing or LT4 replacement were generally weak. A notable exception was the higher odds of direct LT4 replacement in nonurban areas. Geographical variation in decisions to replace LT4 for subclinical hypothyroidism is known from previous survey studies of GPs, albeit at the level of language regions.³⁷ This tendency toward proactive LT4 replacement in non-urban areas may be explained by a lower rate of referral to endocrinologists compared to urban areas, as hypothesized in a Spanish study that found a relevant dependence of TSH testing rates on urbanity.¹⁵

We found a degree of variation between GPs in terms of MOR values in the order of magnitude of the associations with other covariates. This was particularly striking for repeat TSH testing, where the heterogeneity between GPs played a role similar to that of TSH levels and previous primary care contacts, suggesting potentially unwarranted variation. While previous studies have suggested heterogeneity among physicians in their management strategies for patients with hypothyroidism,^{16,37} our analysis is the first to provide a measure from clinical practice that can serve as a starting point for building initiatives aimed at improving quality of thyroid care.

Strengths and Weaknesses

A major strength of our study was the use of a large data set representative of German-speaking Switzerland. In contrast to previous studies that derived evidence from case-based vignettes, we were able to reflect the actual behavior of GPs using real-world routine clinical data. In particular, we were able to examine decision-making as based on actual thyroid function levels and on information about comorbidities as available to the GPs. In addition, we were able to retrieve a population of patients who did not present in clinical situations that would have led to special considerations by the GPs, such as pregnancy.

One limitation was the lacking access to data on presenting complaints and preferences of patients. GPs may have taken these into account when making decisions about TSH monitoring and LT4 replacement, possibly contributing to the observed associations with overt hypothyroidism. We also observed that documentation of body mass index (BMI) was not available for more than half of the included patients (possibly due to documentation in the clinical notes), and we refrained from including it in the regression model to avoid artifacts due to selection bias. In addition, the FIRE database does not contain information on referrals to endocrinologists. However, additional diagnostic procedures requiring specialist care, such as ultrasonography, are generally not recommended immediately after an initial detection of TSH elevation.^{12,22}

Although it is conceivable that GPs may have referred a proportion of patients to specialist thyroid care, this population (which we would have misclassified as not receiving TSH monitoring) may still be considered to have received inappropriate care, as repeat TSH testing for confirmation should precede specialist referral in most cases.

While the cohort of GPs contributing data to the FIRE project is broadly representative of GPs in German-speaking Switzerland in terms of demographics, it is known that a substantial proportion of Swiss GPs were still using paper-based records during the study period.⁴¹ In addition, participation in the FIRE project is voluntary, which may have introduced an additional selection bias in favor of GPs willing to contribute their data, thus biasing our results in the direction of higher quality of care.

The lack of upper reference limits of TSH for many patients was another limitation. The reference limits of TSH are subject to controversy, and the use of adapted reference levels has been advocated, especially for older patients.³¹ The imputed upper reference limits may partially explain the low rates of FT4 measurement at inclusion and of repeat TSH testing during follow-up. However, these rates remain alarmingly low even for moderately and severely elevated TSH at inclusion. In addition, the sensitivity analysis using a considerably lower imputed upper reference limit of 4.0 mIU/L yielded results consistent with our main analysis and did not affect our conclusions. In particular, only an additional association of repeat TSH testing with increasing TSH levels emerged and the associations of repeat TSH testing with higher TSH levels were stronger than in the main analysis – not surprisingly, since the low cutoff arguably increased the proportion of patients misclassified as hypothyroid by imputation.

Conclusion

Our study showed that the follow-up of patients with elevated TSH levels in primary care is largely determined by the degree of thyroid dysfunction. However, we identified areas for improvement and unwarranted associations. Particular challenges include the underuse of repeat TSH testing in younger patients with infrequent primary care visits and the potential overprescription of LT4 to female patients and patients in nonurban practices. Standardization of guidelines and the introduction of quality initiatives to improve guideline adherence could help to address these gaps.

Ethics Statement

Since they fall outside the scope of the Federal Act on Research involving Human Beings (BASEC-Nr. Req-2017-00797), the local Ethics Committee of the Canton of Zurich waived ethical approval for studies based on data from the FIRE project (in particular, no patient consent was required due to anonymization).

Data Availability Statement

Despite full anonymization of patient data within the FIRE project, individuals or organizations with access to overlapping data sets may achieve an identification of patients (such as by linkage with health insurance claims data), which would constitute a violation of legal restrictions concerning identifiability of study subjects in Switzerland. Data access requests can be sent to the FIRE research group (fire@usz.ch) of the University Hospital Zurich.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Author Contributions

Conceptualization: L.J., S.Z., S.M. Methodology: L.J., S.M. Software; L.J. Validation; L.J. Formal analysis: L.J. Investigation: L.J. Resources; T.R., J.M.B., O.S. Data curation; L.J. Writing – original draft: L.J. Writing – review and editing; all authors. Visualization: L.J. Supervision; S.M. Project administration; T.R., J.M.B. Funding acquisition; T.R., J.M.B.

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